

MAELSTROM

Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable
RemOval and Management

D6.3

Report on the marine thermoplastic recycling capabilities

11/03/2025

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in chosen demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. Treatments of the plastic litter for their recovery within a circular economy concept are also foreseen. The purpose of the Deliverable D7.1 is to summarize the results of the coordinated efforts of the networking and stakeholder engagement activities carried out to date, concentrating on events and webinars designed to elicit expert opinions and feedback pertinent to the European policy landscape. Ultimately, these strategic networking and engagement activities serve as a means to build the repository of contacts including EU-funded projects, individual experts, and key stakeholders, which is used herein to propose the creation of a Working Group (WG) to assist in the implementation and success of the EU Plastic Strategy. In this regard, the WG, composed of a balanced, diverse, knowledgeable, and experienced cohort of members, is expected to communicate regularly with the European Commission, involve key sectoral stakeholders, and eventually produce a policy brief for the European Commission on key research and innovation priorities for the enablement of the Plastic Strategy.

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List of Acronyms

- ML: Marine Litter
- WP: Work Package
- LLDPE: Lineal Low Density Polyethylene
- ATR: Attenuated Total Reflectance
- DSC: Differential Scanning Calorimetry
- MFI: Melt Flow Index
- PE: Polyethylene
- HDPE: High Density Polyethylene
- UV: Ultraviolet
- Tm: Melting Temperature

1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a four-year project Funded by the European Commission under the H2020 Programme - Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. The project compiles a consortium of 14 international partners led by the Institute of Marine Sciences of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-ISMAR). The project partners span academia and industry, using the expertise of research institutes, enterprises, and NGOs from 8 European countries. MAELSTROM's main goal is to reduce the impacts of marine litter (ML) in coastal ecosystems by identifying accumulation hotspots and removing the existing litter from the coastal seabed and the water column of rivers before it reaches the sea. This action is supported and enacted through a thorough circular economy and societal-oriented solution. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable, and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort ML; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of ML removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort, and recycle all types of collected ML into valuable raw materials for future marketization; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the ML issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for ML removal within and outside the EU.

The project is implementing two innovative and environmentally sustainable technologies to achieve this goal. These technologies consist of a Bubble Barrier to intercept floating and sub-surface litter on rivers before they enter the oceans, powered by sustainable energy derived from innovative floating photovoltaic panels, and a completely new solution for the removal of small and large items from the seabed in the form of a Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, already successfully tested in the Venice coastal area (<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstrom-outputs/#technologies>). An AI-driven robot is used to identify and segregate

plastics collected from the coastal environment, and three new processes have been used to recycle the retrieved organic and plastic litter. These are transformed into higher-value materials whose characteristics, performance, and economic value are assessed for future marketization. The project focuses on the involvement of the local, national, and international stakeholders, paving the way to the long-term adoption of the technologies by the local stakeholders in the pilot areas. MAELSTROM carries out several actions to enhance ocean literacy and community engagement. Frequent public clean-up events situated on beaches in Portugal, Spain, and Italy have provided an engagement and education platform for citizens to improve awareness around the issues of ML and the tools used in addressing the problem. The project team has also organized public demonstrations of the ML removal technologies at several national, European, and international scientific conferences and High-Level meetings. The public demonstration and launch of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the Venice lagoon took place in June 2023, and the launch of the Bubble Barrier in the Porto region will take place in October 2023. These activities involve, inform, and inspire citizens across Europe. The project has delivered webinars and a freely available newsletter designed to communicate both the problems and solutions of ML pollution to a wider audience.

Stakeholders have been involved from the beginning of the project as core actors, each with particular and dedicated levels of communication and involvement. Actors such as environment management entities; waste management and remediation companies; local enterprises and commercial entities; local, regional and national governments; industry partners; civil society; and local schools and community groups, have been closely collaborated with in the design, coordination, and implementation of the project, demonstrating enthusiasm and support for MAELSTROM's contribution to the ML problem. Local management entities such as those in Vila do Conde, Portugal and the Venice municipality, Italy, have been involved from early stages as core stakeholders for the co-design and co-implementation of the ML removal technologies. The academic community are an integral part of the MAELSTROM stakeholders. Through strategic networking, event participation, conference proceedings, and other engagement activities, the project has developed both its status and built an important community of knowledge-holders, experts, and esteemed professionals. This network,

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strategically designed to demonstrate an unbiased, multidisciplinary, and active participation in the knowledge-sharing of diverse schools of thoughts, has been the central foundation for the design of the below-described Working Group.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of:

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2.1 Aim and scope of the Deliverable

This Deliverable 6.3 “Report on the marine thermoplastics recycling capabilities” contains the work carried out in task T6.3 Thermoplastic recycling of marine litter corresponding to WP6 Circular economy and sustainability of the MAELSTROM

project, focusing on mechanical recycling applied to marine waste collected in the Venice Lagoon/coast and the Douro River estuary in Porto.

The aim of this work has been to analyze the marine waste recovered in previous WP, select those that can be recycled and revalued in a feasible way through mechanical recycling (compounding), and obtain a plastic material with improved properties.

This work has consisted of, on the one hand, collection, cleaning, and sorting of the waste, and on the other hand, mechanical recycling itself, whose phases have been:

- Shredding process of this waste to homogenize its size.
- Extrusion of the shredded material to obtain pellets to manufacture the compounds to be studied,
- Formulation of compounds using a twin-screw extruder from the extruded materials. Regenerating additives, stabilizers, and compatibilizers will be added to these extruded materials to improve their properties and be reused in suitable applications,
- Characterization of the manufactured compounds, for which the necessary test specimens have been manufactured by injection to carry out the characterization of the different formulations.

An exhaustive analysis of the results obtained has also been carried out, and a series of conclusions have been drawn from the entire recycling study.

2.2 Short state of the art of mechanical recycling of plastic waste

The intelligent technology for the sustainable management and disposal of marine waste (MAELSTROM) aggregates and integrates the latest findings in marine litter science, with a powerful combination of automated systems designed for plastic removal and plastic regeneration. MAELSTROM will strive to provide technological answers and solutions to the complex question of whether floating litter from rivers should be intercepted and removed, considering the balance between the positive effect of preventing the degradation of microplastics into micro/nanoplastics and the possible negative effects derived from the removal process itself. The efficiency and selectivity of removal technologies and the frequency of removal are key variables to consider in the search for solutions.

These developments and works have been carried out in previous WPs and after the collection of plastics, their recycling must be studied.

Mechanical recycling is the most economical recycling option, as well as the most energy and environmentally efficient. For this reason, it is currently the most adopted by the recycling industry. It involves the mechanical treatment of plastic waste without changing its chemical structure. Figure 1 illustrates the mechanical recycling process of plastic waste.

Figure 1. Mechanical recycling of plastics.

The degradation suffered by plastics from landfills is totally different from that suffered by plastics in the sea. Plastics during their use life suffer different types of degradation. It can be mechanical or produced by microorganisms, but they mainly suffer photodegradation. This degradation is related to the time that the plastic is exposed to sunlight. In addition to exposure during its life of use, plastics are exposed during their life in the landfill, and in the case of our project, during their life in the sea.

The plastics that end up in the sea suffer degradation by fragmentation, which is accelerated by abrasion caused by marine activity, such as waves and currents. In this case, photodegradation by ultraviolet radiation occurs only when the waste is on the surface and is also accelerated by biodegradation by microorganisms. Despite everything, although it is difficult to estimate, it is considered that in the

marine environment this process is extremely slow. In addition, once the plastic is buried in the seabed, the degradation velocity becomes extremely slow due to the decrease in exposure to UV rays, lower temperature, and lower oxygen levels.

Until now, recycling processes have been carried out with plastics that end up in landfills, since collecting plastics from the sea and especially from the seabed is really difficult. This means that the recovered marine plastics that want to be recycled are older than the plastics in landfills, and years have passed before they are collected, so they have had a long time to degrade very slowly.

During the mechanical recycling processes, the chemical structure is maintained but an important limitation of this recycling process is that shredding, extrusion, compounding, etc., can cause scissions in the polymer chains and thermo-oxidative degradation reactions, which shorten the chain lengths and degrade the performance of the recycled material.

By adding suitable additives, antioxidants, stabilizers, compatibilizers, reinforcements, etc., certain properties of the recycled material can be improved due to the regenerating effect they provide.

This type of mechanical recycling is what has been applied to the collected marine waste. This document contains all the work carried out.

2.3 Inputs from other Work Packages

For the development of the work in T6.3, different marine wastes have been received. This waste was collected in the Venice Lagoon/coast and the Douro River estuary in Porto.

The collection has been carried out in WP5. For the development of this task T6.3, plastic wastes have been selected of which there was enough quantity to carry out the recyclability study, that is, from 15 kg of the same waste. It has also been assessed that they are plastic wastes commonly found in the sea and that they are mono-material, easily separated from other materials such as metals.

3 Methodology

The proposed recycling technology for this task was showed in Figure 2. and describes the scope of T6.3. Once the marine waste has been received, a material preparation process will be carried out, consisting mainly of cleaning and size reduction. The plastic waste will be divided into two fractions, a first fraction for the analysis of the degree of degradation/contamination of the sample and a second fraction of greater weight for recycling and new characterization.

The objective is to be able to evaluate the improvement in the properties of the material after reformulation through the compounding process.

Figure 2: Tecnalía plastic recycling methodology proposed for marine waste.

The waste received is composed of 3 different elements (Figure 3):

- Buoy (black, yellow) 30Kg
- Fishing rope 30kg
- Plastic beam 10kg

Figure 3: Received marine waste. Left: buoys and fishing rope. Right: plastic beam.

The work phases carried out are described in detail below: Waste cleaning, cutting and shredding, plastic recycling and reformulating and testing specimen preparation and analysis performing.

3.1 Cleaning

The waste received, as seen in Figure 3, was dirty, especially with mud that had to be removed. In addition, both the buoys and the rope had shells and other marine animals attached to their surface. Of course, all the waste is covered in sea salt. In order to eliminate as much contamination as possible during recycling, it was necessary clean them with a pressure washer, with tap water at pressure of 20 MPa and an approximate a distance of 40cm as is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Waste cleaning process.

The following images (Figure 5) show the appearance of these wastes after cleaning. Figures 5a) and 5b) show remnants of material adhered to the surface of the buoys that could not be removed. These remnants do not hinder the mechanical recycling process, which will be applied in the same way. They might influence the final properties, adding rigidity to the final product similarly to adding a filler. The images also show the rope (5e) and part of a recovered plastic structure we call a beam (5d).

Figure 5: Selected marine waste for treatment: a) Black buoy, b) yellow buoy, c) black oxidized buoy (part out of water) d) plastic beam e) fishing rope.

3.2 Cutting

The waste selected is large objects that cannot be processed directly in the TECNALIA mill. For this reason, the first size reduction is carried out by cutting with

a manual saw. The waste is cut to a maximum size of 15x15 cm, with the aim of being fed through the mill hopper (Figure 6).

As can be seen, after cutting the yellow buoy, it was observed that it was filled with polyurethane foam. This thermosetting material cannot be processed with the rest of thermoplastics, so it was separated manually.

Figure 6: Cut waste: a) Black buoy, b) rope c) yellow buoy d) yellow buoy with the polyurethane foam core.

3.3 Shredding

The shredding process aimed to reduce the size of the plastic to particles or flakes of approximately 5 mm. For this purpose, a co-rotating blade mill with a 5 mm diameter sieve was used. This step was necessary to be able to feed the extruder that allowed work on the new formulations. Figure 7 shows the mill used and Figure 8 shows the material obtained.

Figure 7: Mateu&Solé mill for plastic shredding.

Figure 8: Material after shredding process. a) Black buoys, b) yellow buoys, c) rope on 5mm sieve.

The shredding process was optimal for the size reduction of rigid plastics, obtaining a homogeneous shredding. However, the shredding process could not be carried out adequately with the rope. Although the rope is a polymeric product, this rope can be considered a textile product made from extremely fine polymeric fibers. This means that after the shredding process, a product in the form of small fibers was obtained. These fibers are fluffy and with very low specific density that cannot be fed in the extrusion machine. Consequently, the rope was excluded from the recycling study.

3.4 Extrusion/Compounding

The extrusion process is a process in which a plastic is melted to obtain filaments or profiles with constant section in a continuous process. The compounding process is a specific extrusion process in which different chemical products or fillers are fed into the extruder on the molten plastic in a controlled manner by weight. The compounding extruder is characterized by having co-rotating twin screws designed with different geometries that allow a homogeneous mixing of these additives (Figure 9 left). In this way, new plastics can be formulated by making specific mixtures of plastic and additives to meet a specific requirement or to improve the properties of the plastic. Just after the extrusion process, the filament was pelletized to obtain injection pellets.

Pellets were obtained from all components separately (Figure 9, middle and right).

Figure 9: Left: Extrusion compounding machine from Coperion and Werner used for Maelstrom with a production rate of 10-60kg/h. Middle: Pellet from black buoy, oxidized buoy, and beam. Right: Pellet from yellow buoy.

Three different additives available on the market were used, which are specific for the recycling of polyolefins and are described below:

- **Irgacycle PS 030 G from BASF.** Designing for re-stabilization of post-consumer and post-industrial rigid polyolefins (STABILIZER uses in percentages from 0.1 to 5%)
- **SETAcomp LL 01 from SETA Polymers** is LLDPE functionalized with maleic anhydride. It is used as Coupling agent for Polyethylene (COMPATIBILIZER uses in percentages from 1 to 5%)
- **GRAFTBOND SEBS-MAH 02520 CAF from GRAFT Polymer** is a high-performance maleic anhydride grafted SEBS. It is an excellent additive for material toughening, increasing impact strength and flexural properties. (COMPATIBILIZER uses in percentages from 1 to 5%)

3.5 Injection

Plastic injection is the process used to obtain most of the plastic objects we use in our daily lives. It starts with plastic in pellet format, which is melted and introduced into a mould. Once the plastic hardens, the part is removed from the mould.

The objective at Maelstrom is not to inject parts, but rather test samples to validate the properties of the material and to be able to analyze its processability and future use. For this purpose, a 300KN ARBURG injection molding machine (Figure 10 left) has been used. Test samples of the 4 different pellets samples were injected separately, and also test samples were injected with 2 different mixtures (Figure 10 middle and right): Mix 1 contains material for the different buoys (black + black oxidized + yellow) and Mix 2 contains Mix 1+ beam.

Figure 10: Left: Injection machine Arburg All Rounder 2570C. Middle: yellow buoy testing samples. Right: Mix 1 testing samples.

Figure 11 shows a summary diagram of the process and the steps carried out for recycling plastics recovered from the sea.

Figure 11: MAELSTROM recycling process overview. Buoy, ropes, and one beam collected in Abandoned mussel farm. A lot of material adhered to the surface, making it unsuitable for direct melting. Cleaning with pressurized water equipment, pressure of 20 MPa and at a distance of ~40 cm. Cutting by co-rotative disc blade. Shredding of each material using industrial shredder. Compounding each material and reformulating in an extruder. Testing samples injection.

4 Results

Once the recycling processes for marine waste have been explained, the analyses and tests carried out to evaluate the improvement of the new materials obtained are explained below.

4.1 Test Methods

- **Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR):** The characteristic functional groups, and therefore the chemical nature of the samples, was identified using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy with a Nicolet iS5 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). The analyses were carried out in attenuated total reflection (ATR) mode in the wavenumber range of 4000-650 cm^{-1} , performing 32 scans with a resolution of 8 cm^{-1} .
- **Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):** The thermal transitions of the materials, in this case the melting temperature, was identified by Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). These tests were conducted using a DSC Q100 calorimeter from TA Instruments (TA Instruments, New Castle, USA) under dynamic conditions. The experiments were performed from -90 to 250°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min. All samples were subjected to cooling at a rate of -50°C/min and subsequent dynamic scanning from -90 to 250°C at 10°C/min.
- **Melt Flow Index (MFI):** Melt flow index measurements were carried out using a METROTEC AC device. The flowability of the new formulations was determined using specific load and temperature conditions that are determined previously for each specific sample. Five measurements were taken per formulation.
- **Tensile Test:** Tensile tests were performed on an INSTRON MT 35 Universal Testing Machine according to UNE-EN ISO 527-1:2020 and UNE-EN ISO 527-2:2012 standards. Five specimens were tested per formulation, and the test parameters applied were:
 - **Modulus determination:**
 - Test speed: 1 mm/min
 - Contact extensometer (Reference length: 50 mm)
 - Modulus calculation in the 0.05-0.25% strain range
 - **Break point determination:**
 - Test speed: 50 mm/min

For the purpose of making a comparison, all marine waste materials were subjected to tests to obtain a starting value. Subsequently, the new formulations were subjected to the same analysis and tests. Table 1 shows all the materials and formulations from which pellets were obtained and the analyses carried out. The

yellow lines show the materials that come directly from the different marine wastes. The greens show the mixtures of materials that were made in order to have enough material to carry out the planned tests. The blue lines show the materials formulated with the additives.

Table 1: List of pellet materials and analysis and tests carried out.

Compounds reference	Manufactured Compounds Composition	Characterization Analysis and Tests			
		ATR	DSC	MFI	Tensile
1	Black bouy	x	x	x	x
2	Oxidated black bouy	x	x	x	x
3	Yellow bouy	x	x	x	x
4	Beam	x	x	x	x
5	Rope	x	x		
6	Buoys Mix (MIX1)			x	x
7	MIX1 plus beam (MIX2)			x	x
8	Oxidated black bouy+ 0,4% Irgacycle	x	x	x	x
9	Beam + 0,4% Irgacycle	x	x	x	x
10	MIX2+ 0,4% Irgacycle	x	x	x	x
11	MIX2+ 0,4% Irgacycle + 4% SEBS	x	x	x	x
12	MIX2 + 0,5% Irgacycle	x	x	x	x
13	MIX2 + 0,5% Irgacycle + 5% SETA LL01	x	x	x	x
14	MIX2 + 20%recycled glass fiber			x	x

4.2 Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR)

Figure 12 shows the IR spectra for waste components. All the spectra are similar, and their peaks correspond to polyethylene (PE).

Figure 12: IR spectra obtained for marine waste.

The 5 spectra were compared to the internal library of the ATR and the spectra of the black buoy, oxidized black buoy, and beam have a higher coincidence with the spectra of oxidized PE from the literature than with the spectra of non-oxidized PE. Therefore, we can conclude that all the black materials analyzed have a certain degree of oxidation.

Figure 13 shows the spectra of the recycled materials in a comparative way. Each graph contains the base material in the upper part and the same material with

additives. No variation is observed in them, due to the additive being present in a very low percentage.

Figure 13: IR spectra obtained for the treated recycled materials, compared with their corresponding waste material.

4.3 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The DSC thermograms obtained from the analysis of marine waste are shown below. They show the typical melting and crystallization temperatures of each polymer. The first 4 DSC (Figure 14, a, b, c, d) belong to the buoys and beam, and their T_m indicates that they are high-density polyethylene (HDPE). The last DSC (e) belongs to the rope and indicates that it is a thermoplastic polyester.

Figure 14. DSC graphs for marine waste.

Figure 15 shows the DSC obtained for the recycled material and compared with their original waste. It is observed that in each of the 3 DSC graphs, the variation of the T_m with respect to the T_m of the base formulation is very small, being in all cases slightly lower, falling within the error margin of the measurement technique.

Figure 15: DSC graphs obtained for the treated recycled materials, compared with their corresponding waste material.

4.4 Melt Flow index (MFI)

The following table shows the MFI measured in the different compounds. Each color indicates the compounds to be compared. The white color corresponds to the MFI of the waste that has not been studied comparatively.

Table 2: MFI values for all the material in pellet format

Compounds reference	Material	MFI (gr/10min)
1	Black buoy	1,152
2	Oxidated black buoy	0,86
3	Yellow buoy	2,41
4	Beam	0,26
6	Buoys Mix (MIX1)	1,92
7	MIX1 plus beam (MIX2)	0,75
8	Oxidated black buoy +0,4% Irgacycle	0,951
9	Beam +0,4% Irgacycle	0,24
10	Mix2+ 0,4%Irgacycle	0,76
11	Mix2+ 0,4% Irgacycle +4% SEBS	1,218
12	Mix2+ Irgacycle 0,5%	0,89
13	Mix2+ Irgacycle 0,5% + SETA LL01 (5%)	0,5
14	Mix2+ 20% recycled glass fibre	0,744

It can be observed that the MFI values are different even though all the materials measured are HDPE. This is because the source materials may have been formulated differently or it is also possible that the degradation degree of each material is different, since UV degradation tends to reduce the fluidity of the material. To determine the exact reason, a comparison with the exact commercial reference of the starting material should be done, which is impossible in a waste of unknown origin.

Figure 16: Comparison between MFI values a) Beam and beam with additives. b)Oxidated black buoy and oxidated black buoy with additives c)Mix and all the combination of this Mix 2 with additives (compound references 10,11,12,13, and 14)

In general, it can be concluded that the addition of the Irgacycle additive slightly changes the MFI value (orange columns) and increases when it is added in higher quantities (yellow column). This effect is greater when the compatibilizing agent SEBS is also added (grey column). The opposite occurs when the SETA additive is added (light blue column), which is initially also a compatibilizing agent. In the case of the addition of recycled glass fibers, we see that the value is not affected.

4.5 Tensile Test

All formulations were mechanically characterized. Table 3 shows the results obtained and Figure 17 shows the properties of the waste materials.

Table 3: Tensile test values for all material in pellet format

Compound reference	Material	Tensile modulus MPa	Tensile strength, σ_m MPa	Tensile strain, ϵ_m (Extensometer) %	Strain at break, ϵ_{tb} %
1	Black buoy	723	22,26	11,40	65,5
2	Oxidated black buoy	1021	28,04	10,67	22,3
3	Yellow buoy	440	15,20	12,96	413,8
4	Beam	751	25,61	13,56	32,2
6	Buoys Mix (MIX1)	705	20,54	11,46	48,3
7	MIX1 plus beam (MIX2)	741	24,69	12,98	30,6
8	Oxidated black buoy +0,4% Irgacycle	1031	28,35	10,52	16,9
9	Beam +0,4% Irgacycle	760	24,65	12,36	21,4
10	Mix2+0,4%Irgacycle	705	23,18	13,14	40,7
11	Mix2+0,4% Irgacycle +4% SEBS	641	21,61	14,12	44,7
12	Mix2+ Irgacycle 0,5%	633	22,58	13,79	36,7
13	Mix2+ Irgacycle 0,5% + SETA LL01 (5%)	558	22,48	14,92	36,5
14	Mix2+20% recycled glass fibre	1201	26	9	16

Figure 17; Mechanical properties of waste components.

The mechanical properties corresponding to the waste components are also different, the oxidated black buoy being the most rigid as indicated by its largest tensile modulus. It may be due to the marine residues adhered to its surface acting as inorganic fillers, providing rigidity to the material. The reasons for the difference between waste components may be the same as those cited in the case of the MFI: their different formulations and/or the degree of degradation that may be different in each case. To determine this, comparative studies with a new component should be carried out, but none have been available.

Figure 18 shows the mechanical properties of the rusty buoy and the beam compounded with the stabilizer, while Figure 19 shows the mechanical properties of mixture 2 and its corresponding formulations with the combination of additives at different percentages.

Figure 18: Mechanical properties comparison of the oxidized buoy and beam before and after compounding with stabilizer.

Figure 19: Mechanical properties comparison of Mix 2 before and after compounding with different additives.

Figure 18 shows that the Irgacycle additive shows a slight stiffening (increase in modulus) of the material and decreases the % deformation. Figure 19 indicates that the addition of additives reduces the modulus, especially when the % of additive added is higher and, also, increases the deformation, especially when combined with compatibilizers. It can be said that an increase in the toughness of the material has occurred.

The case of the addition of 20% recycled glass fiber is totally different, since the fiber is added with the aim of increment modulus and strength properties. The increase in modulus and a decrease in deformation, i.e. a toughening of the material, is clearly observed, as expected. However, there has been no increase in strength despite adding 20% recycled fiber. This is because recycled fiber lacks sizing, which is essential in recycled fibers to ensure a good compatibility with the matrix and thus contribute to the improvement of properties.

5 Conclusion

- If the recycled marine litter has to be cleaned before the treatment, this will have a slight impact in terms of business cost as well as LCA. No detailed analysis has been performed about this impact, but it is anticipated to be minimal.

- **All components have been mechanically recycled** without any problems, **except rope.**

The shredding of the rope generates a very fluffy and very sparse material with a low specific density. The feeding of this material in the extrusion machine needs special hoppers. In addition, the salt content can damage the screws.

- By mixing the buoys and beam, a compound has been obtained (MIX2) to which has been added stabilizing agent (Irgacycle PS 30 G) and compatibilizing agents (GRAFTABOND SEBS and SETA Compo LL01) to improve its properties. 4 compounds have been formulated.

Adding Irgacycle PS 30 G to the beam and oxidated buoy, two more compounds have been formulated.

Adding recycled glass fiber to the MIX2, a last reinforced compound has been formulated.

7 compounds have been formulated.

- Thermo-chemical characterization

All waste materials were identified as **high-density polyethylene** for buoys and beams and **polyester** for the rope.

Comparing the ATR, spectra between compounds with and without additives are similar with very slight changes.

The peaks appear at the same wavelength, so **the additives do not affect the chemical nature.**

Comparing the DSC thermograms It is observed that the T_m of the compounds with additives are very slightly lower.

- Physical characterization (MFI)

It could be said that the **MFI, in most cases, increases.** This means that the **processability of some of the new formulations is easier.**

- Mechanical characterization (Tensile Test)

Deformation is the most sensitive property when assessing the influence of stabilizing and compatibilizing additives. In the case of the compounds obtained from MIX 2, **the deformation of all compounds with additives are greater than the mix without additives.**

The addition of recycled glass fiber increases the modulus and reduces the strain, as expected in a reinforced plastic. However, as it is pyrolytically **recycled fiber**, it has **lost the sizing** that makes it compatible with the matrix and consequently **there is no increase in strength.**

The new recycled materials **have improved their elongation**, although the modulus decreases slightly.
In addition, **their processability has also improved.**

The new materials are tougher and better processable, so recycling marine waste by compounding is considered possible for new applications.

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